

Knowledge-Intensive Employment Globally

Angelo Leogrando °

LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

°LUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

The variable "Knowledge-intensive employment, %" in the Global Innovation Index (GII) measures the percentage of a country's workforce employed in knowledge-intensive sectors, such as technology, research and development (R&D), information and communication (ICT), and other specialized professional activities. This variable indicates an economy's ability to generate and sustain jobs requiring high technical and intellectual skills, representing one of the key indicators of innovation. A high percentage of employment in knowledge-intensive sectors suggests that a country is capable of attracting and retaining skilled workers, investing in strategic sectors that drive technological and economic growth. These sectors tend to be engines of innovation, generating added value through the creation and application of new knowledge and technologies. Knowledge-intensive employment contributes to improving economic competitiveness, adaptability to global market changes, and sustainable growth. In summary, this variable reflects the level of technological development of a country and its potential to face future challenges, highlighting the importance of qualified human capital for innovation. The data refer to the period between 2013 and 2022.

Knowledge-Intensive Employment in 2022. The 2022 data on knowledge-intensive employment provide an interesting snapshot of the ability of various countries to generate and sustain a workforce employed in sectors that require highly specialized skills, such as technology, R&D, science, and information. The importance of this metric lies in its direct connection to a country's innovation potential: a high percentage of knowledge-intensive employment indicates a strong capacity for innovation and a robust knowledge-based economy. At the top of the ranking is Luxembourg with an impressive 100%, demonstrating complete saturation of its workforce in knowledge-intensive sectors. This figure is unsurprising, given the small size and highly specialized nature of its economy, which relies on sectors such as finance, technology, and advanced services. Similarly, Singapore (93.9%), with a highly advanced, technology-oriented economy, ranks among the top, followed by Nordic countries like Sweden (88.7%), Norway (82%), and Iceland (81.4%), all known for their high investments in education, R&D, and technological infrastructure. Countries like the United Kingdom (78.7%), Switzerland (79.3%), and the Netherlands (81.7%) confirm their position as global hubs for innovation. These countries boast a long tradition of academic excellence and a strong connection between industry and universities, facilitating knowledge transfer and the creation of knowledge-intensive jobs. Israel (75.1%) also stands out for its vibrant technological and startup ecosystem, attracting specialized professionals from around the world. In the middle tier, countries like France (73.5%), Germany (70.8%), and the United States (72.5%) maintain high levels of knowledge-intensive employment thanks to advanced industries and a solid scientific and technological base. While slightly distant from the top, these nations continue to play a dominant role in the global knowledge-based economy. Italy (54.7%) ranks lower than the European average, indicating some difficulty in creating knowledge-intensive employment. This figure may reflect a lower capacity for innovation and insufficient investment in strategic sectors like R&D and technology. Spain (54.2%)

shows a similar situation, suggesting that both countries may face significant challenges in improving worker training and integration in highly specialized sectors. At the lower end of the ranking, we see major emerging economies such as Japan (38.5%), Brazil (36.2%), and India (23.9%), which, despite their potential, show a limited presence of knowledge-intensive employment. These countries may not be fully utilizing their human resources in advanced technological sectors, partly due to inequalities in the education system or structural barriers that limit access to specialized job opportunities. Finally, many developing and low-income countries, including Bangladesh (9.8%), Uganda (7.1%), and Mozambique (2.5%), show very low percentages of knowledge-intensive employment. In these economies, the lack of investment in educational and technological infrastructure severely limits the growth of knowledge-intensive sectors. The absence of adequate policies for human capital development and the lack of a strong innovation ecosystem prevent these nations from competing globally in knowledge-intensive sectors. In conclusion, the data show a clear polarization between advanced economies, which can create and maintain a highly qualified workforce, and emerging and developing economies, which struggle to provide opportunities in knowledge-intensive sectors. The ability to generate knowledge-intensive employment is a crucial indicator for the future economic and technological development of countries and requires targeted investments in education, innovation, and infrastructure.

Knowledge-Intensive Employment Between 2013 and 2022. The data on knowledge-intensive employment between 2013 and 2022 highlight significant changes, with some nations experiencing substantial growth, while others have suffered severe losses. This type of employment refers to sectors such as technology, research, development, and advanced education, often associated with innovation and sustainable economic growth. Among the countries that have seen explosive growth in knowledge-intensive employment, Cambodia (+3300%) and Tanzania (+325%) stand out. In Cambodia, the shift from a very low value (0.3%) to 10.2% in 2022 indicates rapid industrialization and an enhancement of educational and technological infrastructure. Tanzania also experienced significant progress, although starting from a modest base. This suggests that both countries have invested in technology sectors and education, crucial for sustaining a knowledge-based economy. Qatar (+275.29%) is another example of how resource-rich countries are seeking to diversify their economies by investing in knowledge-intensive sectors. The increase in knowledge workers reflects national strategies aimed at developing sectors like innovation, research, and higher education. European nations such as Cyprus (+103.50%) and Portugal (+96.13%) have also seen marked growth in this sector, consolidating their position among the advanced economies of the European Union. These countries have benefited from European policies supporting innovation and digitalization, contributing to an increase in jobs in advanced sectors. Sweden (+41.24%), Austria (+41.18%), and Germany (+26.65%) are examples of developed economies that continue to strengthen their knowledge worker base. These countries, already world leaders in innovation, have shown steady growth due to continued investment in research, technological development, and high-quality educational infrastructure. Ireland (+32.73%) and Israel (+25.38%) further confirm the crucial role of a highly qualified workforce in sustaining a knowledge-based economy. Despite many countries showing growth, there are several cases of significant decline. Italy (-28.59%), Japan (-28.17%), and Canada (-17.86%) have experienced notable declines. In particular, Italy has seen a dramatic reduction in knowledge-intensive employment, which may reflect a combination of factors such as brain drain, economic stagnation, and insufficient investment in key sectors. Japan, once a global innovation leader, faces challenges related to an aging population and difficulties in attracting new generations of skilled workers. Some emerging countries have suffered devastating losses. Ethiopia

(-82.94%) and Pakistan (-55.97%) have seen drastic drops in knowledge-intensive employment. This may be linked to factors such as political instability, lack of investment in education and infrastructure, and difficulties in attracting or retaining talent. Ecuador (-49.23%) and Peru (-42.04%) have also experienced significant declines, highlighting the structural challenges these countries face in strengthening their knowledge-based economies. In summary, while many countries have made significant progress in expanding their knowledge-intensive workforce, others are struggling to maintain previous levels. Countries that invest in education, research, and development tend to see sustained growth in this sector, while those that neglect these areas risk losing global competitiveness. This type of employment is crucial for modern economic growth and represents one of the main challenges for emerging and mature economies in the near future. The percentage value of knowledge-intensive employment grew on average between 2013 and 2022 from 45.37 to 46.28 units, representing an increase of 45.02%. The top performers are Cambodia with +3300%, Tanzania with +325%, Qatar with +275.29%, Cyprus with +103.50%, and Portugal with +96.13%. The worst performers are Peru with -42.04%, Yemen with -45.33%, Ecuador with -49.23%, Pakistan with -55.97%, and Ethiopia with -82.94%.

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Appendix

Performers	Countries	2013	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
Top Performers	Cambodia	0,3	10,2	9,9	3300,00
	Tanzania	0,4	1,7	1,3	325,00
	Qatar	8,5	31,9	23,4	275,29
	Cyprus	28,6	58,2	29,6	103,50
	Portugal	33,6	65,9	32,3	96,13
Worse Performers	Peru	33,3	19,3	-14	-42,04
	Yemen, Rep.	30	16,4	-13,6	-45,33
	Ecuador	32,3	16,4	-15,9	-49,23
	Pakistan	35,2	15,5	-19,7	-55,97
	Ethiopia	21,1	3,6	-17,5	-82,94

2022

Fonte: Global Innovation Index

Link: <https://www.wipo.int/web/global-innovation-index>